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Research Article

**ROLE OF TEACHERS IN PROMOTING HARMONY AND
TOLERANCE AMONG PHARMACY STUDENTS****Dr. Asif Iqbal¹, Zahida Javaid², Dr. Shafqat Hussain³, Sabahat Parveen⁴**¹Assistant Professor, University of Education, Faisalabad, asifphd@hotmail.com²PhD Scholar, Government College University Faisalabad, zahidajaved@outlook.com³Associate Professor Education, Government College University
Faisalabad, drhssn@yahoo.com⁴Assistant Professor, University of Education, Faisalabad, sabahat.parveenuoe@gmail.com**Abstract:**

The current study was conducted to explore the role of education in promoting religious harmony and tolerance among pharmacy students. The main objective of the study was to investigate the relationship between the two variables. The students enrolled in Pharm-D at GC University Faisalabad were the population of the study. One hundred and thirty students participated in the study. They belonged to department of Pharmacy and selected randomly. Data were collected with the help of self-constructed instrument, Religious Harmony and Tolerance Survey [RHTS]. Pearson r was applied to analyze the data. The reliability of the instrument was .773. The results revealed that there were statistically significant and strong positive correlation among all the indicators of religious harmony and tolerance. No significant relationship between the role of teachers and religious harmony was found. All the indicators of religious harmony are statistically significant with the indicators of tolerance. Further studies may be conducted to train the students to improve religion harmony and tolerance among them at university level.

Key words: *Religious harmony; Tolerance; Pharmaceutical Students; Pharmaceutical Education;***Corresponding Author:****Sabahat Parveen,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Socio-cultural perspectives including religious and spiritual beliefs affect medicine use and devotion. Increasingly communities that pharmacists serve are diverse and pharmacists need to counsel medicine use issues with ethical and cultural sensitivity as well as pharmaceutical competence. There is very little research in this social aspect of pharmaceutical practice, and certainly none conducted in Pakistan (1). Moreover, their study pointed that how patients' articulate religious/spiritual belief affect medicine use; and how pharmacist can handle these issues. (2) highlighted that substance abuse among pharmacists is an important issue with serious consequences ranging from personal and professional problems to harming patients as a result of poor judgment or medication errors. Most professionals who have become impaired because of substance abuse recover and return to practice. These both issues can be solved by developing religious harmony and tolerance among pharmacist from their university life.

For the last few years, the evils of religious violence and sectarian terror have instigated immense detriment to Pakistan's collective benefits in which we have sacrificed thousands of expensive lives and patent cracks in the society with the sever blockage of economic development in Pakistan. The state itself responsible for promoting ideologies that have cultivated extremism. The debates among and within religions expanded for centuries, in recent era Pakistan is under dire consequences by the religious groups. The reason of such violence are animosity speeches and literature that is promoting faith-based vehemence in Pakistan (3). The need of battling extremism from a combined platform is helpful but it seems important outside intellectual circles to abide by the rights of religious groups living in colleges, schools and universities (4).

According to (5), the change of wrong religious beliefs is not possible to implement by force because they are not subjected to will and nature of humanity. Education and educational institutions are significant for giving young people the awareness and skills essential for their active participation in a state's civic, political, social, economic and cultural life. Universities are also seen as significant for transmitting values, attitudes and identities to new generations (6). Moreover, educational institutions are places where many people share ideas, learn and work on a daily basis. For students and teachers, it is a very important to interact and engage in such a social environment. Their relations at universities determine how they recognize themselves in daily life and more generally, how they identify themselves as part of

the wider society. As (7) says that the existence of cultural and religious diversity gives strength to several challenges regarding the parameter and association. Among the critical issues are how people can articulate themselves as individuals and/or members of groups with different cultural, religious, political and other affections and attachments. According to (8) the idea of religious coherence may be promoted to solve challenges arose in religious discrimination in a global world. All religions must increase mutual sympathies dialogue about justice and peace through collaboration and foster inter-religious and intra-religious harmony. The negative use of religion must be opposed and there should be strict laws regarding the religious violence and extremism (9).

In all societies of the world, harmonious relationship must be encouraged, and religious beliefs must be tolerated. In a multi sectarian society, a common problem occurs between minority and majority. The both groups make it sure must not torture and violate the religious festivals. The utmost responsibility in civilized world is to care for religious feelings. Before highlighting the suggestions to promote religious tolerance and harmony in Pakistan. Combating religious disorder and intolerance have need of education. Laws are essential but not satisfactory to counter the religious mess and intolerance at the individual level (6).

There are common forms of tolerance like discrimination, violence and injustice. It is needed that understanding about respect for gender, religious choices and diversity among people must be developed. The religious, culture and language diversity is the need to inculcate among students. Intolerance may cause disasters between societies and nations. Higher education is the tool to promote tolerance among sects and nations (10).

Religious discord and intolerance rooted in fear and ignorance among nations, cultures and religions. The universities inculcate the ethical values among young scholars with love and passion. They should preach about religious harmony and tolerance especially in multi sectarian society (11). However, education is an all-time practice and should continue till higher level. Activities to build religious harmony and tolerance through education must be practiced everywhere in schools, at home, and in the workplace. The struggle for peace requires proper feedback and legislation. The state must enforce laws to deal with religious conflict and intolerance logically.

Religious discord becomes threatening when it is encouraged to defensive aspiration from groups and individuals. Definitely, the scholars are

representatives of love and harmony. Therefore, institutions may solve political and social issues that create intolerance. It helps in reducing prejudice, propaganda and negative influence. Besides, war with religious dispute and intolerance need local solutions too. It is fact that tomorrow's problems will be more and more inclusive¹. The universities and civil society should promote and support religious harmony and tolerance through the replace of ideas and culture (12). Any attempt to powerfully impose on students may create intolerance, aggression and bereavement (13). Tolerance can be countered by making laws against offenders, promoting education on harmony and tolerance, Access to information, individual awareness and through local solutions². The main root causes of intolerance is lack of knowledge, ignorance, and view the world in black and white with no grey zones. The prejudice and religious biasness are the reasons to fuel intolerance. The challenge to the status quo is another threat to nation's stability (10).

Significance of the Study

Pakistan is facing many problems of which are bomb blasting, discrimination, sectarianism, and intolerance. It is mocking and regrettable position that, in spite of being affectionate supporters of Islam, on harmony, peace, and tolerance. Muslims, around the world are flattering gradually more intolerant. The pharmacist are considered life savers as like doctors and it is seen that pharmacists are forbidding people from implementing their religious believes. Moreover, the lack of tolerance is also evaluated in several pharmacists, which can lead patient to disappointment. This study will find out the level of religious harmony and tolerance among pharmacy students. By this study we can find out the role of education in promoting religious harmony and tolerance. The results will help to plan of action to reduce the intolerance and religious discord among students and will promote harmony without uniformity.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Objectives of the study

Following objectives were made:

1. To compare the elements of religious harmony between male and female students.
2. To compare the aspects of tolerance between male and female students.
3. To investigate the role of teachers in promoting religious harmony among pharmacy students.
4. To study the role of teachers in promoting tolerance among pharmacy students.

5. To find out the relationship between religious harmony and tolerance of pharmacy students at university level.

Hypotheses

To achieve the required objectives, following hypotheses were formulated:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between religious harmony and tolerance of male and female students.

H₀₂: There is no role of teachers in promoting religious harmony and tolerance among pharmacy students.

H₀₃: There is no relationship between the indicators of religious harmony and indicators of tolerance among pharmacy students at university level.

*2: *Road to religious Harmony (2015). Published in Dawn, July 30th, 2015*

*1:

<http://www.un.org/en/events/toleranceday/background.shtml>

LIMITATIONS

Keeping in view the time limit, the study was limited to only pharmacy students that are enrolled in last semester at Government College University, Faisalabad. It can be enhanced on other departments and other level of students

NATURE OF STUDY

This was quantitative research design in nature. Survey method was used to collect the data.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE

The population of the study comprised all the Pharm-D students studying in GC University Faisalabad. They were selected randomly from department of Pharmacy. One hundred and thirty students were approached to collect the data.

Data Analysis**Table 1: Number and Percentage of Male and Female Students**

Gender	N
Male	85
Female	45
Total	130

The number of males is 85 and number of females is 45. So majority of male students participated in the study.

Table 2: Number and Percentage of Male and Female Students belong to Departments

Departments	Frequency
Pharmacy	130
Urdu	0
Psychology	0
Sociology	0
Total	130

The table 2 revealed that students belong to pharmacy department were 130 students.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between religious harmony and tolerance of male and female students.

Table 3: Relationship between Religious Harmony and Tolerance of Male and Female Students

Indicators	Gender	Sig.
Religious Harmony	.056	.001*
Tolerance	.781	.004*

****P<0.01, N=130**

The table 3 revealed a significant relationship of role of teachers and religious harmony at university level. The relationship between the gender of teachers and tolerance is strong positive and significant as $p < 0.01$.

H₀₂: There is no role of teachers in promoting religious harmony and tolerance among pharmacy students.

Table 4: Role of Teachers in Promoting Religious Harmony and Tolerance

Indicators	Teachers	Sig.
Religious Harmony	.813**	.000
Tolerance	.267**	.003

****P<.01, N=130**

The table 4 revealed strong significant and positive relationship of role of teachers and religious harmony at university level. The teachers promote the religious harmony among the students. The relationship between role of teachers and tolerance is also significant and positive. Although there exists a weak and but positive relationship.

H₀₃: There is no relationship between the indicators of religious harmony and indicators of tolerance among pharmacy students at university level.

Table 5: Relationship between the Indicators of Religious Harmony and Indicators of Tolerance

Indicators	Education role	Teacher role	Student role	Curriculum	Gender
Teacher role	.046				
Sig	.616				
Student role	.497**	.361**			
Sig	.000	.000			
Curriculum	.269**	.438**	.475**		
Sig	.003	.000	.000		
Gender	.327**	.504**	.493**	.527**	
Sig	.000	.000	.000	.000	
Overall	.406**	.784**	.734**	.711**	.759**
Sig	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

P<0.01, N=130

According to table 5, all the indicators of religious harmony are statistically significant with the indicators of tolerance. Moreover, they have strong and significant relationship among them. It revealed that religious harmony promotes tolerance among pharmacy students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

No significant relationship of role of teachers and religious harmony at university level was found among pharmacy students with respect to gender. The relationship between the gender of teachers and tolerance is positive, strong and significant.

There exists a strong significant and positive relationship of role of teachers in promoting religious harmony at university level among the students of pharmacy department. The teachers promote the religious harmony among the students. The relationship between role of teachers and tolerance is also significant and positive. Although there exists a weak and but positive relationship.

All the indicators of religious harmony are statistically significant with the indicators of tolerance. Moreover, they have strong and significant relationship among them. It revealed that religious harmony can promote tolerance among pharmacists of future.

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